

Evaluating the 2025 Grade 4 English VPR Using Bachman and Palmer's Assessment Framework

This study assesses the unified monitoring of the All-Russian Verification Work (VPR) in English for 4th-grade students. In Russia, 4th grade marks the end of primary school, with all students nationwide completing the standardised VPR assessment. The demo version of VPR 2025 is provided in Appendix A.

The VPR in English aims to evaluate 4th graders' educational outcomes by the Federal State Educational Standard for Primary General Education and the corresponding federal program. Results serve for interim certification, improving teaching methods, and analysing local and regional education systems. The assessment determines students' language proficiency and informs potential adjustments to the curriculum.

The quality of the English VPR materials is evaluated using Bachman and Palmer's (1996) model across six parameters: reliability, construct validity, authenticity, interactiveness, impact, and practicality. The analysis aims to find what works well and what can be improved to make the test more effective and meaningful for students and educators.

1. Assessment materials overview

This is an Achievement Test designed to assess the extent to which students have mastered the material taught by the curriculum for English as a foreign language in Grade 4. All tasks included in the test correspond to a basic level of difficulty.

The test includes four tasks, each assessing a specific language skill. The listening task evaluates students' ability to understand and extract specific information

from a spoken text. It is designed to reflect familiar school-related topics and everyday situations, and students are expected to select the correct answer from a list of options after hearing the recording twice. The reading task assesses the ability to identify specific information in a short narrative text. Students read a passage and then answer multiple-choice questions based on their comprehension.

The grammar task tests students' knowledge of important grammar rules and how they use them in context. The task is a gap-fill exercise inside a short and clear text, so grammar is checked in a real communication, not just by itself. The writing task is a form-filling exercise that checks if students can give basic personal information in English. Students must find important details from a short biography and write them in a simple, organised table.

2. Evaluation of the 2025 Grade 4 English VPR

Criteria described by Bachman and Palmer (1996) provide a clear framework to analyse the quality and effectiveness of language assessments by examining aspects such as reliability, validity, authenticity, interactiveness, impact, and practicality.

2.1. Reliability

The 4th-grade English VPR test demonstrates several strengths in terms of reliability, which refers to the consistency and dependability of test results (Bachman & Palmer, 1996). The test structure is clear and uniform: students receive explicit instructions for each section, and tasks are largely based on objective item formats, such as multiple-choice and short answer. These tasks reduce scorer subjectivity and promote stable scoring across different testing contexts—instructions in L1.

Furthermore, clear scoring keys and rubrics are provided, especially for Task 4 (writing/form-filling), where criteria for content and spelling are explicitly outlined.

Despite these strengths, the test does include open-ended tasks, where minor spelling issues may cause inconsistencies in scoring, especially among young learners who are still developing spelling skills. A good assessment should understand that one type of task is not good for every student, especially in classes where children have different needs and ways of learning (Chapman & King, 2012). The VPR test is very standard and the same for all students. It cannot be changed or adapted for children who learn differently. There are no special options for students with learning difficulties like dyslexia or dysgraphia. The test also does not consider different learning styles. For example, visual learners may find the test boring or difficult because there are no pictures, diagrams, or other visual parts to help them understand better or stay interested.

2.2. Construct Validity

The construct validity of the 4th-grade English VPR test is generally adequate, as the test includes tasks that target core skills such as listening, reading, grammar, and writing, which are part of the Grade 4 curriculum. Most VPR tasks correspond with curriculum expectations and target relevant domains of English language use for young learners. The tasks use age-appropriate vocabulary and grammar and avoid overly complex or abstract formulations.

However, construct validity is not only about technical alignment with curriculum objectives—it also includes the social and educational consequences of assessment

and its connection to meaningful, real-world communication (Changing Minds, n.d.). As Messick (1989) and Gipps (1994) argue (as cited in Brady, 2012, p.32), a test cannot be considered valid if it leads to negative or limiting outcomes for particular groups of students. For example, while aligned with curriculum goals, the grammar task (See Figure 1) is situated in a contrived context that does not resemble natural language use. The topic of Lake Baikal does not reflect students' personal experience. Although it is a real place, it feels distant and abstract for many children, especially those living in big cities who have never been there (almost all Russian children). This reduces personal relevance and engagement.

ВПР. Английский язык. 4 класс. Образец

Код

3 Прочитай рассказ. Вставь вместо каждого пропуска, обозначенного буквами А–Е, нужную грамматическую форму, выбрав её из трёх предложенных вариантов (1, 2 или 3).

Lake Baikal

Last year I visited Siberia. I **A** _____ Lake Baikal. It is a very beautiful deep lake. It is also the **B** _____ freshwater lake in the world. It is 25 million years old. There are about 100 volcanoes but there are **C** _____ active ones. 336 rivers flow into Lake Baikal. Only one flows out, which is the Upper Angara. There are more than thirty rocky islands in this lake. One of them is Olkhon. A lot of people **D** _____ it every year. Lake Baikal is home to thousands of different plants and animals. People like taking photos of **E** _____.

A 1) see	2) saw	3) seeing
B 1) oldest	2) older	3) old
C 1) some	2) any	3) no
D 1) visit	2) to visit	3) visiting
E 1) they	2) them	3) their

Запиши в таблицу выбранные цифры под соответствующими буквами.

Ответ:

A	B	C	D	E

Figure 1

Task 3 from the Grade 4 English VPR 2025 demo version.

Note. Adapted from All-Russian Verification Work (VPR) Demo 2025, Grade 4 English, Federal Institute for Pedagogical Measurements (FIPI), <https://fipi.ru>

The text seems written mainly to practice grammar. The sentences are designed to fit specific grammatical forms rather than to tell an interesting or meaningful story. For example: "Lake Baikal is a very beautiful deep lake. It is also the B_____ freshwater lake in the world." These sentences are correct, but do not sound like natural communication for children.

Another key aspect of construct validity is the variety of evidence a task allows (Brady, 2012). The more diverse the way students demonstrate their learning, the more valid the task becomes. However, the VPR offers only narrow task formats (multiple choice, gap-fill, short answer), without room for extended production, alternative modes of response, or student choice—essential elements for capturing the abilities of diverse learners.

2.3. Authenticity

As defined by Bachman and Palmer (1996), Authenticity refers to how closely test tasks reflect real-life language use and communicative situations.

Brady and Kennedy (2012) suggest that a test to demonstrate true Authenticity must simulate the kind of challenges and language tasks students might face outside of school. The VPR does not include tasks that reflect real-world "tests of ability" such as conversations, problem-solving with language, or expressing opinions—features that would help students demonstrate a fuller range of language knowledge and use.

However, Task 4 (see Figure 2) — "Help your friend fill out an online profile" — shows moderate Authenticity. It mimics a real-life situation in which a student reads a short biography and completes a simple form with personal information. The language

is age-appropriate, and the task includes familiar themes (family, school, hobbies, food), which makes it accessible and somewhat engaging for young learners. Using a profile format reflects forms students may encounter in modern digital life — e.g., registration forms on websites, apps, or class activities — thus increasing functional Authenticity. Similarly, the listening task (Task 1), where a girl tells her mother about her school day, has elements of natural communication. It reflects familiar everyday language and contains situational elements that students can relate to.

- 4 Помогите своему другу заполнить анкету для сайта «Друзья онлайн». Прочитайте текст и запишите информацию в таблицу. Под каждым номером запишите только одно слово (без артиклей). Числа необходимо записать словами.

Tom Ivanov

Tom is from Russia. He is 9 years old. Tom lives in Saratov, in Russia. He has got a younger sister and an older brother. The children have got a cat. Tom likes playing football. He wants to be a professional football player in the future. He is a good pupil. His favourite subject is Maths. He likes juice but he doesn't like milk.

Name	1.
Age	2.
Country	3.
Number of children in the family	4.
Pet	5.
Favourite subject	6.
Favourite drink	7.
Favourite sport	8.

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Figure 1

Task 4 from the Grade 4 English VPR 2025 demo version.

Note. Same source as Figure 1.

It is important to consider that the Authenticity of Task 4 is limited by its format and purpose. The student is not communicating with a real partner or expressing personal ideas — they are transferring information from a text to a form. While this may check basic comprehension and vocabulary, it does not involve real communication, interaction, or personal expression. There is no decision-making, audience, or communicative goal beyond completing the table. This task is more about accuracy and reading for detail than meaningful language use.

Also, the restriction to "one word only" and prohibition of articles removes the natural form of language. This format trains students to adapt to test conventions, not real communication. For example, students must write "Maths" instead of "His favourite subject is Maths," which reduces the opportunity to show understanding of sentence-level meaning and productive skills.

2.4 Interactiveness

Interactiveness refers to how much the test requires students to actively use language skills and engage with the tasks (Bachman & Palmer, 1996).

In the Grade 4 English VPR, interaction is low. Most tasks are receptive, like choosing answers or filling gaps, which means students mostly recognise or copy information. Task 4 (see Figure 2) requires active interaction as the student must extract and record specific information from the text. This is a minimal form of interactivity, but it still involves comprehension and processing of information. No real communication scenarios exist where students interact or make decisions in English.

In short, the test needs more interactive tasks to assess real language use better and engage learners.

2.5 Impact

The test matches the curriculum goals, ensuring that what students learn and are tested on fits well together. The clear and simple scoring helps teachers see how students perform and plan their next lessons. From a bigger view, the VPR lets schools and regions compare their students' results easily. Such standardised feedback can motivate schools to improve instructional quality, which is an intended positive impact.

The VPR test also has several limitations in terms of impact. One is the potential for washback, where teaching and learning focus narrowly on passing the test rather than broader language development.

Chapman and King (2012) also say that tests like the VPR, which are the same for everyone, often do not consider students' different needs. Because of this, some students with special learning needs or different backgrounds can feel left out. This can make these students less motivated, especially if they find the test hard or the questions don't fit how they learn.

While some students may feel motivated by the challenge and clarity of the test, others may experience anxiety or disengagement due to its rigid format and perceived high stakes.

2.6 Practicality

Practicality refers to how feasible and effective it is to administer, score, and interpret an assessment in real educational settings (Bachman & Palmer, 1996). A practical test combines thoroughness and ease of use within the school's time, resources, and expertise.

The VPR test has a high practicality score. It is made so students can finish it in one lesson, about 45 minutes, so it fits well in a normal school schedule. Most tasks are closed-type, like multiple choice and fill-in-the-blanks, which makes it easier for students to answer and for teachers to mark. This helps teachers have less work and gives more fair and quick grading. The test contains clear, detailed keys and rubrics, especially for the open-ended writing task (task 4), which helps standardise assessment and supports teachers with different levels of assessment experience (Kohn, 2006). In terms of resources, the test does not require special equipment or materials beyond basic classroom resources, which increases its accessibility in different school contexts.

It is essential to recognise that the reliance on closed-response items limits the depth of student responses and may not fully capture complex language abilities.

Conclusion

The 4th-grade English VPR test is well organised and easy to use. It is reliable because it has clear instructions and answer keys that help teachers give fair marks. The test fits well with what students learn in their school program, so it checks the skills the curriculum requires. Tests listening, reading, grammar, and writing in ways that

match the topics and language level of 4th graders. Also, the scoring system is clear, so teachers know how to give points for each task.

However, the test can be better if it includes more real-life tasks that feel like real communication. Many questions are multiple-choice or gap-fill, requiring students to recognise or choose answers. Adding activities where students have to speak, write freely, or work with others would be good. For example, a role-play or a short conversation could help students practice speaking skills. Or writing a letter or a story could show how well they can use English independently.

Adding these tasks would make the test more interesting and help teachers see how well students use English in real situations. It would also help students be more confident and ready to use English outside the classroom. So, while the test is good for checking basic knowledge, it could be improved by focusing more on real communication and active language use.

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Appendix A

The demo version of VPR 2025

ВПР. Английский язык. 4 класс. Образец

Код

1 Ты услышишь сообщение. Для каждого предложения А–Е выбери один правильный вариант ответа из трёх предложенных (1, 2 или 3). Ты услышишь текст дважды.

A. What do you know about Jane?

- 1) She is a pupil.
- 2) She is a new teacher.
- 3) She is a pupil's mother.

B. What subject is the girl going to have a test in?

- 1) English.
- 2) Music.
- 3) Maths.

C. What is the girl's favourite subject?

- 1) English.
- 2) Music.
- 3) Maths.

D. What does the girl hope to do at the English lesson? She hopes to ...

- 1) learn new words.
- 2) sing a new song.
- 3) meet a new teacher.

E. What does the girl want to do after the lessons? She wants to ...

- 1) listen to music.
- 2) do her homework.
- 3) eat pizza in the café.

Запиши в таблицу выбранные цифры под соответствующими буквами.

Ответ:

A	B	C	D	E

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ВПР. Английский язык. 4 класс. Образец

Код

2 Прочитай текст. Для каждого предложения А–Е выбери один правильный вариант ответа из трёх предложенных (1, 2 или 3).

John Brown

John Brown did not have any brothers or sisters. He was an only child. John lived in a big city near a river but he liked to go to the park in the afternoon after school when the weather was nice. He walked in the park and looked at other boys who played football there.

When it rained, his mum took him to the library where John chose a book to read. He liked reading very much. He enjoyed books about pirates and space explorers but he did not like fairy tales.

When John was ten years old his father said that he did not have a job any more. John's parents decided to sell their house in the city and move to a small village. John was both happy and sad. He enjoyed living in a big city but he was happy because he hoped to have a lot of adventures in the countryside.

A. How many children were there in John's family?

- 1) one
- 2) two
- 3) three

B. What did John do in the park?

- 1) He played football.
- 2) He read books.
- 3) He walked.

C. What books did John like reading? He liked ...

- 1) books about football players.
- 2) books about adventures.
- 3) fairy tales.

D. What happened when John was ten years old?

- 1) His dad found a new job.
- 2) His father lost his job.
- 3) His father bought a new house in a big city.

E. Choose the true sentence.

- 1) John did not like his big city.
- 2) John hoped to have new adventures.
- 3) John didn't want to move to the village.

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Код

ВПР. Английский язык. 4 класс. Образец

Приложение 1

Текст для аудирования

Сейчас ты будешь выполнять задание по аудированию. Ты услышишь запись дважды. После первого и второго прослушивания у тебя будет время для выполнения и проверки задания. Все пары включены в аудиозапись. Остановка и повторное прослушивание аудиозаписи не предусмотрены.

1 Ты услышишь сообщение. Для каждого предложения А–Е выбери один правильный вариант ответа из трёх предложенных (1, 2 или 3). Ты услышишь текст дважды.

Мы готовы начать.

Hi, mum. This is Jane. I'm at school and I'm going to have a Maths test. I always do my homework, so I think I will get a good mark for the test. After the Maths test, I am going to have an English lesson. I like this subject very much. I think we will learn some new words. The last lesson today is Music. By the way, we have a new teacher. Her name is Anna Smith. I hope we will listen to some wonderful music at the lesson and learn a new song. After the lessons I want to go to the cafe to eat pizza with my classmate Kate. I'll come home at 3 p.m. and I'll do my homework after having lunch.

У тебя есть 30 секунд, чтобы записать ответы в таблицу.
(Пауза 30 секунд.)

Сейчас ты услышишь текст ещё раз.
(Повтор.)

У тебя есть 30 секунд, чтобы проверить свои ответы.

Задание завершено.

Время, отведённое на выполнение задания, истекло.

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